

Social Policy Recommendations

MAY 2025

EUROPEAN IDENTITY THEFT OBSERVATORY SYSTEM

FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101073928

Policy Recommendations

Preventive

1. EU Funding for social IT literacy projects

Create a supplementary funding system addressed with Schools, Universities and non-profit Associations with digital purposes with the possibility of:

- (a) educating on online risks and social vulnerabilities and strengthening computer literacy
- (b) structuring a continuous co-training process «top-down» and «bottom-up» to design new forms of support and assistance to OI DT victims and users.

Supportive

2. Provide clear and easy-to-understand psycho-social tips and guidelines

Associations dealing with victims of OI DT should continue to develop and share clear and easy-to-find information on the path that the victim should take on how to be practically and emotionally supported after reporting.

3. Periodic data collection of socio-demographic and experiential data

Establish an EU research team that periodically submit questionnaires across Europe to keep the data updated by socio-profiling the OI DT victims and their needs.

Foster the European LEAs a public sharing of periodic internal reports on the most frequent OI DT case studies and profile of the victims.

4. Fostering collaboration and creating a network of OI DT associations and psychologists across Europe with a living document.

Promote the existence of a «living document» for OI DT victims called «find psycho-social help» to easily identify and update information on active structures on the European territory.

Recovery

5. Allocate EU funds for the activation of vouchers for OI DT victims' support

Create vouchers and agreements - for specific low-income groups - for access to legal and psychosocial support.

6. Foster the activation of information desks for OI DT victims

Allocate funds to enhance the psycho-social support directly within the Police Department or within the Victims' Associations linked to the LEAs information points.

Policy Implications

1. **Education** in terms of socio-digital literacy is a very important factor in increasing attention to social risks and vulnerabilities.

Annual or biennial investment based on competitive calls **prepare** users, **encourage** bottom-up dialogues by **increasing engagement and empowerment**.

2. Greater **clarity of information** on the steps to follow and on the psycho-social-legal support services available in the area would **reduce individual vulnerabilities and the feeling of loneliness** that often leads victims to give up reporting.

3. **Organizing information** through **skilled and authoritative research teams** is essential **to find verified indications, understand and compare the issue** from a social and experiential point of view.

4. **Defining a victim support network** within the digital space-time is fundamental to provide useful information to both victims and helpers.

5. The **victim recovery** must consider also individual and contextual inequalities that may limit access to practical and emotional resources by minimizing a resilient attitude. For these reasons, **allocate funds** is necessary to ensure the care recovery.

6. **Establishing OI DT information desks** with staff who act as **key points for victims and their caregivers** is crucial to encourage reporting and support often complex **victims' bureaucratic process**.

Project Details

Project Name

The European Identity Theft Observatory System (EITHOS)

Coordinator

DR Dimitrios ZARPALAS
CERTH

Programme - call topic

HORIZON-CL3-2021-FCT-01-12
Online identity theft is countered

Duration

3 years
October 2022 - September 2025

Budget

€ 2,996,141.25

Social Media

EITHOS_EU

eithos_eu_project

Eithos - Horizon Europe project

EITHOS_EU

Website

<https://eithos.eu>

Contact

eithos_coordination@iti.gr

FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101073928